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Humanising Machines or Mechanising Humans

Artificial Intelligence: Issues & Perspectives

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Abstract:

It is common to speak of the AI revolution as though it is an event that is expected to take place in the future, but in fact this event has already begun, and we are, unbeknownst to most of us, riding the crest of the wave. The enormous potential that AI hints at, which is currently in our hands, forces us to confront the hard questions of what it means to be a human and what it means to be a machine. Many of these questions have had no clear answer from the beginning of civilisation and rational discourse, and will probably never have an answer that satisfies everyone. In the midst of this uncertainty, AI intrudes as a hugely disruptive technology. Those who exhort caution are frequently caricatured as conspiracy theorists, but as James Barrat says, AI may very well be our last invention, not because AI would necessarily turn out to be evil as in some Sci-Fi movie, but because human agents may be identified as inefficient bottlenecks in the calculations of a superintelligent AI optimised for efficiency, and with no malevolence whatever, it may override our plans just nonchalantly as we think nothing of stepping on insects as we go about our daily lives. Provided this does not happen, and the AI we create retains the goals given to

it initially by human programmers, such a subservient or co-operative AI could indeed prove to be a highly useful tool that boosts our rational investigation and technological prowess to an almost infinite degree.

Keywords: *Superintelligence, AI Singularity, Futurology, Artificial General Intelligence*

Introduction

In June 2022, Google engineer and whistle-blower Blake Lemoine published chat transcripts indicating that an artificial intelligence chat program (named LaMDA) created by Google has claimed to be conscious (Schneider & Papazoglou, 2023). Just last month, it was revealed that several financial articles in CNET had been authored by its AI program (Ropek, 2023). The lines between the social roles played by man and machine are fast becoming blurred. “What does it mean to be a human? What does it mean to be a machine?” – these questions are now being asked with increasing urgency.

Saint Augustine’s quip on time is almost a cliché: “What then is time? Provided that no one asks me, I know. If I want to explain it to an inquirer, I do not know (Hernandez, 2016).” From the attempts of scholars to articulate what we think we know about being human, we reasonably conclude that much of what it means to be human is similarly ineffable (Holt, 2022). This state of semi-ignorance about ourselves on account of human finitude (Moore, 1992), has led religious writers to speak of the “mystery of human personhood. (Cardinal Dulles, 2015)”

The Contingencies of the Present

Human civilisation is at the cusp of creating “Artificially Intelligent” entities that, if current trends of technological capability are anything to go by, will be capable of intelligent activity (i.e., capable of applying rational principles to problems and coming up with a solution), learning (i.e., capable of starting from first principles and understanding specific concepts and developing specific skills that were not taught), interaction with humans in a way indistinguishable from other humans, self-modification (both on the hardware and software level), and goal-oriented behaviour.

This revolution forces us to confront several hard questions that we have had the luxury of leaving up in the air until now, since we have been the sole conscious, rational, learning, cultural species on this planet. Some examples of these are: what does it mean to be a human? What does it mean to be conscious? What does it mean to have a “self?” What is the relationship between sentience, sapience, reason and intuition? How can a claim of being self-aware or conscious be validated? Is the brain just a machine? Can the operation of the human brain be replicated on a computer? These are not questions from armchair philosophers. Very soon, if the current trend continues, we will be face to face with computers running AI algorithms that claim to be self-aware and conscious. How will we react to these claims? What legal and moral rights will we be willing to concede to these AIs? (If this last question seems like a page out of Isaac Asimov, it would be pertinent to point out that we have already paved the way for this dilemma by ceding legal and moral rights (and even legal personhood) to one highly powerful and influential non-human entity in today’s society: the corporation (Parkinson, 2020), and Saudi Arabia set a precedent by granting citizenship to a robot in 2017 (Reynolds, 2018).)

Our Unpreparedness for the Inevitable Future

The more we try to grapple with the implications for AI, the more we are brought to realise that we don’t yet have a species-wide consensus about the various dimensions of being human. Until recently, we understood our humanity almost exclusively through religious lenses, and we have largely replaced these with rational, historical, mechanistic, probabilistic and ideological lenses with changes in culture, economy, social structure and scientific knowledge. If we are to make sense of AI and answer the question of whether (and if so, how exactly) they are different from us, we need a philosophy of human; in effect, we need a new moral philosophy. Religion was very good at this job, but the technocratic cultures that are driving the AI revolution are not particularly enthusiastic about moral philosophy (Kissinger, 2018).

Even as recently as a decade ago, it was possible for technological experts to scoff at the possibility of hard AI or Human-Level Artificial General Intelligence (i.e., an AI that is not just good at specific tasks like cleaning or industrial assembly, but can learn to do any task autonomously, much as a human can). Hayward (2004), a polymath and writer, was dismissive of the reality of general AI, on the basis of the anthropology of St. Maximos Confessor. However, with the current rate of progress in AI, such emphatic denial has given way to acceptance of the inevitability of the development of Strong AI (Sweeney, 2019), mostly because AI algorithms demonstrated at least some capability in several competencies which were claimed to be unique to humans. For instance, while “intuition” was long held to be a major human domain that would differentiate us from AI (Larkin, 2022), recent advances in AI have cast doubt on this (Ravisetti, 2022), especially when the AI named AlphaGo defeated the world champion in the game of Go, a highly intuitive game humans have been playing for millennia (Stoltzfus, 2018). When authors like Asimov were writing about self-aware robots, there was no possibility of them existing for real. The hardware to implement AI did not exist then, nor did any realistic means to train an AGI. But today we have both the technology to build the necessary hardware and the biggest possible dataset in human history to train an AI to understand human concerns – the internet itself (Anany, 2023)!

The sensible thing to do would be to postpone our project of facilitating an AI Singularity until we have achieved some clarity on these important issues. (Superintelligence or AI Singularity refers to AI becoming capable enough of modifying its own software and hardware, and thus increasing in capability at an explosively exponential level, which no human technology development cycle can hope to even approach – and if this sounds too much like science fiction, the fact that AIs are already acing coding tests should give us pause (Elias, 2023)). Among the worried voices pointing out that humanity is intellectually and philosophically unprepared to make sense of AI has been Kissinger (2018). The specifics of the future

may be yet uncertain (Smith, 2022), but the general consensus is that AI superintelligence is inevitable (Dilmegani, 2023), because there are simply too many competing stakeholders in the race to develop the next AI breakthrough that none of them can afford to sit back and let competitors have the advantage – witness the frenetic rush of Google, Baidu, and Alibaba to release competitors to ChatGPT once Microsoft announced its integration with Bing (Roose, 2023). Ironically, the Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT)-3 language model which makes ChatGPT possible was constructed partly upon the transformer algorithm open-sourced by Google in 2017 (Coldewey, 2023)!

The Impossibility of Opting Out

Given this dilemma, one might think that those who don't wish to be involved in these messy decisions could opt out of the AI revolution. But the truth is that unless small groups want to set up disconnected low-technology luddite enclaves similar to the Amish, Bedouins or the Meivazhi Saalai experiments, all of us are going to be involved in this situation willy-nilly. What many of us don't realise is that we already interact with Artificial Intelligence algorithms on a daily basis (Reese, 2020). AI already functions as the backbone of online retailing, travel, search engines, healthcare administration, medical data processing, diagnostics, surgical procedures, stock trading, social media curation, education, translation, document processing, agricultural monitoring, drone warfare, entertainment production (including pornographic content (D'Mello, 2018)) and viewership analysis, journalism, news curation and readership analysis - and has even encroached into supposedly quintessentially human fields like legal judgements (Stanly, 2023)! The recent furore created by ChatGPT's ability to help students cheat on assignments is only a small foretaste of the sweeping changes that the field of education is going to experience in the near future. In governance, AI is already being implemented in surveillance and police-work (Russia's efforts in this area are well known (Evdokimova, 2022)), but very few of us are aware of the DRDO's NETRA – an AI programme spying on civilians in India for almost a decade now (Parbat,

2013)), prediction of potential risks to public safety and in reducing bureaucratic workload. Campaigns are underway to lobby for a ban on the potential AI arms race that looms in the horizon, hoping to attach a public stigma to the production of AI weapons much like the stigma that exists regarding chemical and biological weapons today (Tegmark, 2018).

The AI revolution is not in the far-off future. It has been with us for quite some time now, growing silently and unobtrusively, until it is so much a part of our lives that we don't notice how much we have come to rely on Artificial Intelligence in our daily lives. Granted, all the above applications still rely on what is called Narrow AI (that which is good at learning to do a particular task well, often even better than humans, but is no good at any other task). It is the consensus that an Artificial General Intelligence (AGI) which by definition is good at learning to do anything at human-level or better, is not the same as clubbing together various Narrow AIs, but involves a new type of meta-learning ability. However, if and when such a milestone is reached, it will be a minor matter for such an AGI to take control of all the existing Narrow AIs, especially if the AGI is deployed by a corporation which has a controlling stake in diversified businesses.

Conceptualising Intelligence and Life

An instance of our confusion is that while we discuss intelligent machines, we are yet to reach consensus on the nature of intelligence. Tegmark (2018) skirts this controversy by using an intentionally vague and broad definition that posits that intelligence is the ability to achieve complex goals. This definition avoids the situation of getting trapped in endless debates about the exact nature of intelligence. This definition allows us to come up with another insight: we can assert that AIs can have goals, without having to first answer the question of whether AIs are conscious. Guided missiles have goals, as have software that trade on the stock market or dynamically fix prices for commodities on online retailers.

Another insight about intelligence that was instrumental in driving the AI revolution is that intelligence is, for all practical purposes,

substrate-independent (Tegmark, 2017). This means that the same algorithm can be implemented on different underlying hardware technologies. This has been the foundation of the computer revolution from the days of analog computers through the multiple generations of digital computer architectures. In the initial days of computing this insight was expressed by the use of NAND and NOR gates as universal gates to implement any logical function. In these days of AI, the universal atomic computational structure is the Artificial Neural Network, which is in the last analysis an algorithm, and can be implemented on various hardware platforms, with the caveat that more advanced platforms are required to run more computationally intense algorithms in meaningfully short time frames.

If we then conceptualise humans as composed of carbon-based complex organisms constructed and operated according to programming stored in genetic protein structures (i.e., DNA), then the progress of culture and learning in each generation can be considered as software installed on top of this hardware. Evolution has optimised the human body and brain to be self-replicating and to function on the lowest available energy, but AIs don't have to operate on the same limitations. Thus, we arrive at a comprehensive model of the history of life on Earth: the first generation of life like bacteria and plants were unable to change either their hardware or their software at will, and changes could happen only through the slow process of evolution. The second generation of life, which is humans, could change their software but not their hardware. AI can be viewed as the third generation of life on earth, which will be able to change both hardware and software at will. This model makes it possible for us to view AI as the next stage of life (which is silicon based instead of being carbon based as we are, and has the luxury of using energy intensive mechanisms for operation and self-replication (Tegmark, 2017b)).

AI as the Descendants of Humanity

There is also the possibility that benevolent AI will, like intelligent and dutiful children assisting incompetent parents, be

able to solve most of the large problems facing humanity like resource redistribution, energy crisis, social stability, etc. Elon Musk is well known for his proclamation that if humanity wants to survive, it must become an interplanetary civilisation. But after Mars, what next? Terraforming other planets in the Solar System does not seem very feasible. Perhaps we could try their moons which have subsurface water, like Ganymede or Titan, but after that there's really not much more to look forward to, unless we stripped an entire planet like Venus or Mars to build a giant space station or multi-panel Dyson Sphere orbiting the Sun to harvest energy (Dimitropoulos, 2022). Even at this point, we reach a dead end, since the other nearest star systems are hundreds and millions of light years away. Barring the invention of warp engines or some other kind of faster-than-light travel, we aren't going to become an intergalactic civilisation in any realistic sense. Here AI offers us a chance to spread out across star systems and galaxies, since the lifetime of inorganic hardware is not limited as organic human bodies are. Further, once a reasonably complete manufacturing unit is setup on a planet, the population of the planet by AI can proceed by building hardware out of the raw materials available on the planet, and when a sufficient hardware platform is available, AI can be transmitted to the planet wirelessly, cutting short the expense and time of travel, much like several versions of free/open-source OSes are literally all around us, in the form of digital transmissions. The germ of this idea was already tossed about more than a decade ago (Slakey, 2008), and its full implications are now being discussed (Rees, 2016).

Hard Questions About This Next Stage

But if AI is the next stage of life, does it have all that we have and more, or is it a hollow imitation of us with no one really home within? Will these AIs have feelings, consciousness, morals, self-awareness, and free will? If AI is about learning and seeing patterns, can we speak of virtues and vices of AI? If AIs are considered to have free will, what legal rights do they deserve (Eliot, 2022)? What legal culpability do they have and how will we penalise them? What would be the legal status of AIs created by "uploading" a digitised model of a particular human mind onto a computational architecture

(Deigin, 2021)? Is there any guarantee that AIs beyond the singularity will retain the goals human programmers have set for them, or will they, like children turned adults and free from the obligation of obedience to parents, set new goals for themselves? If this happens, do we even have the moral right to resist or would we be obliged to bow out and let AI take over the universe, since they are superior beings to us intellectually? Will AI revere us as their creators, or will they treat us with the same indifference we give to our unicellular evolutionary ancestors (Reese, 2020)?

Humanising Machines – a Long Latent Trend

Wrestling with these concepts shows us that the swelling wave of AI forces us to consider what it means to be human, what it means to be a machine, and where the dividing line is to be found. In effect, we are faced with the latest avatar of one of the oldest problems in philosophy: the mind-body problem. The humanising of the machine begins with the “polite convention” proposed by Alan Turing (Michie, 1993). This states that just as we don’t attempt to prove the consciousness of our fellow humans, an AI that acts and speaks indistinguishably from human beings must be given the courtesy of being considered conscious. The Dartmouth Proposal built on this foundation when it proposed that learning can be modelled and thus mechanised (Veisdal, 2021). The Physical Symbol Hypothesis of Newell and Simon (Nilsson, 2007), as well as the Strong AI Hypothesis of Searle (Melnyk, 1996) further blurred the line between man and machine, asserting that AI would have a mind in the same sense that a human did. Dreyfus (1974) asserted that the nervous system could be modelled by a device but also pointed out that such copycat modelling was in itself an admission of ignorance about the nature of the mind.

While these and other similar questions may give philosophers sleepless nights, they seldom prey on the minds of AI creators since deciding whether an AI is conscious has no bearing on the feasibility of constructing an AGI, which is mostly all that excites makers.

The Flip Side: Mechanising Humans

Consciousness is generally understood as the ability to have mental states (Ferguson, 2022) or subjective experiences (Tegmark, 2018). But if contemplating the ability of AI to possess consciousness leads to humanising machines, likewise, trying to pin down the exact nature of human consciousness very easily leads to mechanising humans. When “uploading” mental states is under consideration, it leads to modelling a human as just one out of infinite possible arrangements of quarks, thus needing nothing more than quantum physics to explain the mind (Buchanan, 2011) and do away with the soul (the Cartesian “ghost-in-the-machine” dualistic soul, at least; the non-dualist idea of the soul held by Aquinas and other Classical thinkers(Wood, 2019) obviously remains unaffected by this.) One prevailing view sees the relationship between mind and brain as that of software and hardware. This idea has a respectable pedigree, from Hobbes, Leibnitz, Hume, Kant and down to Putnam and Fodor today (Dennett, 1998). If consciousness is just an emergent property, are we humans merely machines who have the illusion of consciousness and free will? If we are then merely cogs in a larger planetary system, could it be possible for the Earth as a whole to have a kind of consciousness beyond our comprehension? (Ideas once considered exotic, like the Gaia Hypothesis, have now been given a new lease of life in this context (Powell, 2019).) By that logic, would the “consciousness” of AI be as incomprehensible to us as ours is to an ant?

Attempts to Impose Order on the Impending Chaos

The EU’s guidelines for Trustworthy AI (AI HLEG, 2021), the Vatican’s Rome Call for AI Ethics (Lubov, 2023), Tegmark’s Asilomar AI principles (Future of Life Institute, 2022) and many such other ventures are indicative of the urgency that drives the movement for ethical guidelines in AI development. But how meaningful are these? Once AI superintelligences roam freely across our communication networks, what sort of society would the human-AI interaction result in? Tegmark (2018) speculates on the various eventualities that could materialize viz., libertarian utopia, benevolent dictatorship, egalitarian utopia, gatekeeper AI, AI as Hidden god, AI as Enslaved god, AI as conqueror of humanity, AI as descendent of humanity, Zookeeper AI, and Orwellian AI. He also

considers the possibility that a spooked humanity intentionally regresses technologically (a la Frank Herbert's *Dune*) as well as the possibility that humanity self-destructs long before AI has a chance to be born. In the "AI as descendants" scenario, exemplified by Hugo de Garis, humans accept their transient role in the evolutionary process and willingly acquiesce in being supplanted by AI as the dominant species in the universe (Ford, 2021). The "AI as enslaved god" scenario is the one in which these ethical development guidelines make most sense. In those scenarios in which AI dominates humans, or in which one group of humans rules over society through a subservient AI, the Nietzschean truth that one only has what rights one can grab is validated, and human agency is eliminated or severely curtailed. In the libertarian and egalitarian utopia scenarios, these ethical standards would still make sense except that AI would no longer be tools of humanity but would have a say of their own regarding their role in society. They might even be our collaborators in answering the thorny philosophical issues surrounding AI, to say nothing of scientific discoveries in other fields. In such a situation, until we have a complete understanding of consciousness and other issues, it might be apt to grant AIs a quasi-personal legal status, (i.e., recognise a state of 'robohood' or 'electronic personhood' – which can be conceptualised as a limited subset of rights considered innate to humans (Graaf, 2022) - instead of the more complicated 'personhood' (Hildt, 2019), though even this proposal is not without controversy (Negri, 2021)) modelled on the consideration of corporations as legal persons.

An Unsatisfying and Not Very Hopeful Conclusion

This tentative speculation outlined above is the best that can be said about the situation for now. If we are unable to end our considerations of the implications of AI for our near future on a more hopeful or concrete note, it is because honesty compels us to acknowledge the extreme and unprecedented uncertainty towards which humanity is rushing at full speed, surfing the wave of the AI revolution towards the creation of something we may not even be able to comprehend, much less control. After

all, Dr. Frankenstein at least knew what he intended to create, whereas we will probably have to wait for our brain-child (pun intended) to explain itself to us – if it thinks such explanation worth its time!

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